

D11.3 Risk and vulnerability & LCA/LCC integration – Month 18

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
API	Application Programming Interface
AR6	Sixth Assessment Report (IPCC)
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers
BIM	Building Information Modeling
BMS	Building Management Systems
CSTB	Centre scientifique et technique du bâtiment / Scientific and Technical Centre for Building
CIR	Circularity Index Rating
D#.#	Deliverable #WP number #Task number
DSS	Decision Support System
EEA	European Environment Agency
GIS	Geographic Information System
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HDF	Hierarchical Data Format
HIBOU	Hybrid assessment of the Interactions between the BiODiversity, the nature-based solutions, and the Urban system
INN	Innovation
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISPRA	Institute for Environmental Protection and Research
IUHI	Urban Heat Island Intensity
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
MCDM	Multi-Criteria Decision-Making
NBS	Nature-Based Solutions
PAI	Hydrogeological Setting Plan
PDH	Personalised Data Hub
SLIDE	Simplified Landscape Irrigation Demand Estimation
UBEM	Urban Building Energy Model
UHI	Urban Heat Island
UTCI	Universal Thermal Climate Index
WP	Work Package

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the development of a consistent and integrated assessment framework within the WILSON project, aimed at supporting sustainable renovation, environmental performance improvement, and climate resilience in buildings and districts. The work establishes harmonized methodologies and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), supported by calculation methods and digital tools designed to enable informed, multi-objective decision-making.

At the core of the framework is the HIBOU method (Hybrid assessment of the Interactions between Biodiversity, nature-based Solutions, and the Urban system), an integrated approach that evaluates the environmental footprint of renovation strategies, including climate change impacts (based on Life Cycle Assessment), biodiversity (ex situ and in situ), and Urban Heat Island (UHI) effects. This method enables a systemic understanding of the interactions between built environments, ecological systems, and climate-related pressures.

Complementing this approach, the Risk & Resilience Assessment Tool provides a structured methodology for assessing climate risk, exposure, vulnerability, and resilience in asset management and renovation planning. It supports stakeholders in quantifying potential losses, identifying critical vulnerabilities, and strengthening adaptive capacity across multiple hazard scenarios. Together, these tools allow for a comprehensive evaluation of renovation actions in terms of both environmental performance and long-term resilience.

In parallel, the report advances an initial assessment aimed at developing practical guidelines for integrating Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) into Building Management Systems (BMS), within BIM (Building Information Modelling) and Digital Twin environments. This integration enhances the ability of stakeholders to compare design alternatives, identify trade-offs between environmental and financial performance, and prioritize renovation strategies aligned with sustainability objectives. By embedding environmental and economic indicators directly into operational digital platforms, the framework promotes more transparent, data-driven and participatory decision-making processes.

A key achievement of this work lies in the development of a common ontology and structured methodology that harmonizes diverse indicators related to material resource consumption, climate change mitigation, biodiversity, risk, and resilience. The report also identifies the principal challenges associated with integrating LCA and LCC into operational digital systems, including methodological complexity, data availability constraints, and the need for technical capacity-building among stakeholders.

Finally, the report emphasizes the strategic importance of developing an interoperable IT structure capable of integrating and harmonizing heterogeneous data flows across multiple digital applications. Such interoperability is essential to ensure that robust, coherent and comparable information reaches end users, enabling the evaluation of “as-is” and “to-be” scenarios aligned with environmental, financial and sustainability goals.

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1. Scope of the deliverable

Urban areas are increasingly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, with extreme weather events such as prolonged heat waves being exacerbated by the urban heat island (UHI) phenomenon. Given that more than half the world's population [1] resides in cities, addressing climate-related challenges in these environments has become an urgent priority.

Effective resilience planning in urban contexts requires a deep understanding of the complex interactions between buildings, infrastructure, and environmental factors. To support adaptive measures, a holistic and integrated assessment framework is crucial. Such a framework helps inform strategies that maintain essential functions and promote sustainability in the face of changing climate conditions.

Within this context, the present deliverable introduces two integrated methodologies aimed at enhancing climate resilience and reducing climate risks and vulnerabilities in the built environment. It provides a detailed description of the implemented methodologies alongside the associated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to be applied throughout the WILSON project. Additionally, the deliverable proposes a methodological approach for integrating Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) into Building Management Systems (BMS) to support sustainable building management.

2.2. Structure of the deliverable

The present deliverable is structured into 9 chapters. The Executive Summary and Introduction chapters provide the document's preface. Following these, the deliverable is divided into two main parts. The first part addresses the work related to Task 11.3, entitled *Risk and Vulnerability*, while the second part focuses on Task 11.4, dedicated to "LCA/LCC: environmental & social assessment on BMS". Both parts are organized similarly and include common sections such as a detailed description of the methodological approach and its application within the Italian pilot. The final chapter, "Conclusions," provides a discussion of a summary of the developed methods and outlines forthcoming actions.

More specifically, the first part is divided into the Methodological Approach, which includes a brief overview of the HIBOU method. This section further elaborates on the selected model used to develop the Urban Heat Island-related risk indicator. Special emphasis is placed on the ongoing developments of the Green Roof, Soil, and Vegetation models, which will assess the mitigation impact of Nature-Based Solutions addressing the Urban Heat Island effect in the Italian pilot. Additionally, the Risk and Resilience deterministic tool is presented, along with the guiding principles of its methodological approach. The risk and vulnerability indicators, as well as their application within the WILSON project, are detailed.

The second part is structured around the Methodological Approach, presenting a state-of-the-art review of LCA and LCC methodologies. It provides a high-level overview of the technical requirements for the correct application of an environmental and economic assessment to the different WILSON's case studies. Furthermore, it aims to analyse the

complex connections between WILSON's IT structure, data sources and set of tools, highlighting obstacles and feasible solutions to implement during the second phase of this activity, Task 12.4. The outputs of this report will be the starting point for the development of actual technical guidelines that will support stakeholders and BMS users to accurately implement and understand LCA and LCC within the framework of sustainable building management.

2.3. Relation with other tasks and deliverables

This section provides a brief overview of the indirect or "anchored" connections between the current deliverable and the other Work Packages (WPs) within the WILSON project. It also outlines the relationships with specific deliverables that have already been submitted or are in the process of being submitted. More specifically:

- **WP1 – Management and Coordination:** This deliverable is related to WP1, specifically to Deliverable *D1.3 – Data Management Plan*. D1.3 outlines the data management and sharing protocols, detailing the data categories and formats that will be utilised in the modelling of risk and vulnerability indicators.
- **WP4 – Baseline assessment and performance indicators of buildings and portfolios:** This deliverable is linked to WP4, particularly the following deliverables:
 - *D4.1 – Detailed Models of Buildings at Demonstration Pilots*, which includes the detailed description of the Italian pilot where the risk and vulnerability indicators developed in the current deliverable will be applied.
 - *D4.2 – WILSON Use and Business Cases Definition*, which defines Use Case 5, focusing on the Risk, Resilience, and Biodiversity Nexus and thus the HIBOU method discussed further.
 - *D4.5 – WILSON KPIs Life Cycle Oriented Indicators Panel*, which collects and summarizes the KPIs that are further processed and analysed in the current deliverable.
- **WP9-10 – Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for non-energy uses:** This deliverable is connected to WP9 and WP10, specifically to Deliverable *D9.4-10.4 – Material Passports for Sustainable Renovation*. D9.4 focuses on the development of the digital workflow *INN7-Continuum*, which provides the input data necessary for the risk and vulnerability modelling discussed in the current deliverable.
- **WP11-12 – Digital twin enabled lifecycle data solutions for non-energy uses:** This deliverable is linked to Deliverable *D11.2 – D.12.2 – Methodology for Climate and Biodiversity Impacts*, which defines the *INN6-Environmental Performance Toolset* or HIBOU method. This method is closely related to the Urban Heat Island risk indicator presented in the current deliverable. Additionally, D11.2 provides a comprehensive state-of-the-art review of LCA practices across Europe, which supports the second part of this report.
- **WP13 – Integration of Technologies and Preparation for Large-Scale Pilots:** This deliverable is related to WP13, where the *INN8-Risk and Resilience Assessment tool* will be implemented as part of the preparation for large-scale pilot activities.
- **WP14 – Large scale demonstration campaign:** This deliverable will be linked to D14.1 and will document the activities carried out in the Italian pilot. It will focus on the demonstration of **UC5 – Risk, resilience and biodiversity nexus** and **UC6 –**

Renovation planning and design. In detail, the methodology developed in this document will be applied to the Italian Pilot.

PART I: RISK AND VULNERABILITY

3. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

3.1. INN6 HIBOU Method

With the aim of developing an interdisciplinary, multi-criteria assessment tool for the integrated, reliable, and scalable evaluation of urban renovation and expansion projects, CSTB introduces the Hybrid assessment of the Interactions between the Biodiversity, the nature-based solutions, and the Urban system (HIBOU) methodology [2], as depicted in Figure 1. This approach enables decision-makers to access quantitative KPIs across a wide range of domains and spatial scales, including:

1. Climate risks
2. Biodiversity
3. Water management
4. Environmental footprints
5. Health and well-being
6. Economy

Figure 1: Graphical representation of the HIBOU methodology.

Within the framework of the WILSON project, specific KPIs related to Environmental Footprints, Biodiversity, and Climate Risks will be applied and evaluated. These include indicators such as Global Warming Potential, Ex-situ and In-situ Biodiversity, and Urban Heat Island Intensity. In alignment with the objectives of this report, only the latter will be described in detail in the following sections. For a comprehensive explanation of the overall methodology, readers are referred to Deliverable D11.2 – Methodology for Climate and Biodiversity Impacts.

3.1.1. Urban Heat Island Assessment within HIBOU

The integration of the Urban Heat Island (UHI) phenomenon into the HIBOU multicriteria framework was initiated as part of the WILSON project, marking the first step in adapting

HIBOU to account for UHI impacts. Two methodological approaches can now be incorporated, depending on the spatial scale of the study area.

At the city or territorial scale, CSTB has developed a geospatial tool to estimate a suite of decision-support indicators, including Urban Heat Island Intensity (IUHI), potential mitigation capacity (Δ UHI), associated mitigation costs (ϵ UHI), and heat-related vulnerability (HVS), as detailed in [3]. These indicators are combined into a comprehensive cost-benefit metric ($\epsilon\Delta$ UHI), which serves to prioritize mitigation actions across the urban area. This tool employs the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) in combination with Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) techniques [4], enabling a thorough assessment of urban heat risks and mitigation strategies over large spatial scales (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Urban Heat Island Intensity (IUHI) mapping of urban units in the city of Paris [5] produced using the geospatial tool.

For smaller spatial scales, such as neighbourhoods, street canyons, or individual buildings, CSTB has developed a physics-based coupled micro-modelling tool (Figure 3). This system integrates an Urban Building Energy Model (UBEM) with a detailed microclimate simulation engine, specifically targeting the urban canopy layer where localized phenomena and interactions between built structures and microclimate are most significant. At this scale, a detailed and flexible 3D micro-model is required to accurately represent the diverse components of the urban environment. The tool produces a comprehensive set of outputs, including wind speed and direction, surface and air temperatures, shortwave and longwave radiation, energy demand, and more, across discretized urban surfaces or building zones. Additionally, it facilitates the extraction of key performance indicators (KPIs) related to Urban Heat Island intensity and thermal comfort for both indoor and outdoor environments.

Figure 3: Urban Heat Island Intensity (IUHI) mapping across varying urban canopy heights for a neighbourhood in Paris, generated using the microclimate tool [6].

Between the two tools, **the micro-scale modelling approach is more suitable for the objectives of the WILSON project and the scale of the Italian pilot site.** It will be implemented to evaluate the impacts of urban expansion and renovation strategies of an Italian district. The following sections provide an overview of this model and describe the recent enhancements made to incorporate Nature-Based Solutions (NBS).

3.1.2. Urban Building Energy & Microclimate model

UBEM – DIMOSIM

DIMOSIM [7] is a comprehensive simulation platform designed to evaluate the feasibility, design, and operation of district energy system concepts (Figure 4). The tool integrates (a) models of buildings and thermal zones, (b) models of thermal and electrical networks, and (c) a range of energy system components covering different scales, including emitters, hydronic distribution systems, production units, storage, and control mechanisms. Developed progressively at CSTB (Centre Scientifique et Technique du Bâtiment, Sophia-Antipolis), DIMOSIM has benefited from contributions through various national and European research projects.

The tool is distributed through multiple channels. It is available as a commercial application with a user-friendly interface via the PowerDIS and UrbanPrint platforms. Additionally, it can be accessed as a Python library, providing greater flexibility for custom workflows, or through the dedicated Dimosim API for programmatic integration into specialized pipelines.

Figure 4: Overview of the simulation capabilities of DIMOSIM.

Input data

The tool requires three types of input data:

1. Hourly Climate data which can be under a standardized format (.epw)
2. GIS data of buildings,
3. A set of simulation parameters (.json) in which thermal zone and system parameters are introduced.

Simulation Workflow

The simulation pipeline, as shown in Figure 5 (left panel), is divided into three main stages. First, the object creation module processes the input data and generates the various objects, such as thermal zones, energy systems, and related components. Second, the sizer module assigns nominal values, sizes the elements, and precomputes several parameters, while the simulator object establishes the simulation sequence (e.g., district generator, building heat exchanger, thermal zone emitter) and performs the main calculations. Finally, upon completion of the simulation, the assessment module can be executed to compute and provide KPIs.

Data Storage

Simulation results are archived using multiple file formats to accommodate different analysis needs, including plain text files, CSV tables, and the Hierarchical Data Format (HDF5). This flexible approach ensures compatibility with large-scale data management, while preserving the structure of the computed results.

Validation

During installation, Dimosim's building model undergoes a Python-based validation test following the BESTEST (ASHRAE) protocol. The tool's outputs are compared against the BESTEST reference averages and ranges, and the installation is considered successful only if the test executes correctly, with the computed loads and temperature values falling within the prescribed acceptable thresholds.

Urban microclimate – EnviBatE

EnviBatE [8] is a research microclimate simulation platform developed in Python programming language (3.11V actual release) with performance-critical routines optimized using Cython, that incorporates distinct submodules integrated into a unique simulator. The model integrates:

1. a thermal surface model,
2. an airflow model integrated to a zonal urban canopy model,
3. a solar radiation algorithm (a ray-tracing model is also available for specific applications), and
4. a parameterized soil and vegetation models

The following subsection presents the necessary input data along with the simulation workflow.

Input data

The tool requires three types of input data:

1. Hourly Climate data which can be under a standardized format (.epw)
2. GIS data of buildings, trees and open spaces or 3D models in specific format (.skp)
3. A set of simulation parameters (.yaml) along with elements description (.xml) in which thermal and optical parameters are introduced.

Simulation Workflow

Following the import of input data, a mesh generation algorithm is executed to construct the distinct meshes required for solar radiation, airflow, and zonal calculations. Once generated, an indexation procedure is applied to ensure the interconnection among the different meshes, as well as the mapping between urban surfaces and canopy air cells, thereby enabling the representation of their interactions.

The preprocessing stage concludes with the computation of solar radiation and airflow fields, together with the assembly of the matrix system, within which the energy balance equations are applied and solved iteratively over the simulation time loop. The resulting variables include building thermal demands, canopy-cell air temperatures, and the surface temperatures of urban elements.

The post-processing stage provides 3D maps of hourly or accumulated values, along with various options for generating diagrams. In addition, KPIs are derived during this stage to support further analysis. The simulation pipeline is illustrated in Figure 5 (right panel), highlighting the workflow and interconnections between the different stages.

Data Storage

The tool employs three primary file formats for data storage. First, detailed numerical values of the computational variables are stored as datasets organized under specific groups in the Hierarchical Data Format (HDF5) [9]. Second, simulation parameters and objects generated during the preprocessing pipeline are serialized using the Python-specific Pickle (binary) format, enabling their reuse in post-processing. Finally, mesh data are stored in a plain text format (MSH), which facilitates subsequent 3D visualization.

Validation

In the absence of an established validation protocol for microclimate simulations, the robustness of the tool is assessed by comparison with full-scale real-world applications and monitoring campaigns (e.g., [10]), as well as against experimental mock-ups, such as scaled-down street canyons exposed to real climatic conditions (e.g., [11]). These studies demonstrate a strong correlation between the simulated results and the measured data.

3.1.3. Co-simulation workflow

The urban building energy model and the microclimate simulation tool have been coupled to enable a holistic and dynamic assessment of the micro-urban scale in terms of energy performance and thermal comfort. This co-simulation approach provides a more detailed representation of microclimate-induced phenomena in building energy simulations, including the precise modelling of solar shading from neighbouring buildings, inter-reflections, and long-wave radiative exchanges between urban surfaces. Furthermore, it allows the assessment of the influence of local air temperatures on building thermal demand, overcoming the limitations of using meteorological station data, which are typically located far from the studied district and do not account for the Urban Heat Island effect.

From another perspective, the co-simulation framework enables the evaluation of the impact of energy systems, such as air-conditioning units, on the local microclimate, as well as the assessment of mitigation or adaptation strategies at the building level on urban microclimate conditions.

The co-simulation is implemented on a dedicated co-simulation platform (Figure 5), which is responsible for generating and indexing the input data shared by both tools. In addition, the platform manages the data exchange during the simulation loops of the coupled models. This communication is based on a socket-based approach, providing a standardized interface for sending and receiving data over network protocols, thereby ensuring reliable and efficient inter-process communication.

Figure 5: Schematic representation of the distinct and coupled simulation pipelines of the UBE and the microclimate model, illustrating data flow, preprocessing, simulation, and post-processing stages.

3.1.4. On-going Developments

Within the framework of the WILSON project, and to address Nature-Based Solutions as a mitigation strategy for the UHI effect, two new modules for the coupled UBEM–microclimate tool are currently under development, according to the HIBOU integrated approach. The first module implements a green roof model, enabling the assessment of the impacts of green roofs on both building energy demand and local climate mitigation. The second module corresponds to a soil and vegetation model, which allows the evaluation of urban greenery strategies aimed at mitigating heat stress and protecting vulnerable populations.

Green roof module

The developed green roof sub-module, based on Sailor’s Ecoroof model [12] is a physics-based energy balance model, currently being integrated into the Dimosim Urban Building Energy Model (UBEM). It is formulated as a two-node model, representing the growing medium and the plant foliage, and can be coupled with the nodes of the UBEM wall model (by default, a four-node wall model). This module allows energy modelers to explore a range of design options, including the thermal properties and depth of the growing medium, as well as vegetation characteristics such as plant type, height, and leaf area index.

The model explicitly accounts for long-wave and short-wave radiative exchanges within the plant canopy, canopy effects on convective heat transfer, evapotranspiration from soil and plants, heat conduction and storage in the soil layer, and moisture-dependent thermal properties. At each time step, the model simultaneously solves for both the soil surface temperature and the foliage temperature. In parallel, a water balance scheme has been developed to account for irrigation requirements and soil moisture dynamics during dry periods, ensuring the viability of the vegetation.

Soil & vegetation module

The development of the soil and vegetation model is based on the same fundamental principles as the green roof model, with additional refinements for increased precision. The primary distinction lies in the model formulation, which supports a more detailed nodal representation. For instance, the soil component allows for up to ten nodes, enabling the simulation to reach ground depths, while the vegetation component is represented as a multilayer system with five nodes to capture air temperatures above and below the tree canopy (two nodes) as well as within the crown at different heights (top, middle, and bottom).

Similar to the green roof model, the soil and vegetation model is formulated according to energy balance principles, where shortwave and longwave radiation, sensible and latent heat fluxes, and precipitation heat flux are calculated for both the vegetation–atmosphere interface and the foliage–ground system under a coupled approach, based on the Army Corps of Engineers’ FASST vegetation models [13].

To incorporate the present model to the microclimate tool, we developed a surface model (as depicted in Figure 6) of the trees crown in which detailed solar radiation is computed for each tree surface as well as wind speed attenuation is applied depending on seasonal crown variations.

Figure 6: Illustration of the mesh representation of an evergreen conifer.

To account for drought conditions and due to the absence of systematic watering schedules for urban vegetation, the Simplified Landscape Irrigation Demand Estimation [14](SLIDE) rule has been implemented and adapted to hourly time steps, in order to ensure a minimum level of performance of urban greenery in mitigating the UHI effect.

3.1.5. Chapter conclusion

In this section, the proposed methods employed to assess the urban heat island effect within the HIBOU framework are presented. Based on the detailed description of the Italian Pilot provided in D9.4, the most appropriate tool that aligns with the pilot's spatial scale and the defined scenarios is selected. This tool is the **physics-based** coupled **UBEM** (Dimosim) – **Microclimate** (EnviBatE) model, which is capable of evaluating both the urban heat island intensity and outdoor thermal comfort through explicit 3D modelling.

Furthermore, we outlined ongoing developments aimed at integrating soil-vegetation and green roof modules into the existing framework to enable a comprehensive evaluation of the impact of NBS in mitigating the UHI effect.

3.2. INN8 Risk & Resilience Assessment Tool

Increasingly severe weather events demand an extensive and multidisciplinary strategy to rate how buildings resist and adapt to changing conditions, especially within diverse urban environments.

The Building Risk and Resilience approach combines wide risk analysis, heritage preservation, sustainability, and circular economy principles, and scenario planning based on climate forecasts, which encourages collaboration among stakeholders and establishes

customized resilience solutions for various building types, focusing on project objectives goals.

This framework permits knowledgeable choices in design, conservation, and management, boosting climate resilience, decreasing risks, and promoting sustainability, all while meeting regulatory and heritage conservation standards.

3.2.1. Analysis of the territorial and climatic context

Assessment process begins by establishing a reference climate scenario, using both historical records and regional projections to identify present and future risks associated with climate change. Critical factors—such as flood events—are evaluated through advanced climate models (including IPCC AR6), hydrological simulations, and regional hazard mapping.

Data is sourced from organizations like CMCC, ISPRA, Civil Protection, and other regional climate databases, enabling the creation of tailored adaptation and resilience strategies for specific sites.

The analysis focuses on the effects of climate change on waterproofing systems, drainage capacity, and structural stability, with particular attention to urbanized and impermeable environments.

The data collection is based on regional sources, climate maps, IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) modelling and local climate databases (for ex. CMCC, ISPRA, Civil Protection).

3.2.2. Inventory of building assets and their characteristics

The Pilot (based on the detailed description of the Italian Pilot provided in D9.4) is organized into three building categories: historic buildings, underground spaces, and newly constructed facilities, each requiring adapted plan of actions for climate resilience.

For heritage structures, interventions must be reversible and non-invasive, such as the use of passive ventilation, subtle drainage solutions, and integrated monitoring technologies. Underground areas are particularly vulnerable to flooding and water infiltration, making waterproofing, pumping equipment, anti-backflow valves, and backup power systems essential. In contrast, new buildings offer opportunities to incorporate bioclimatic design principles, high-performance building envelopes, green roofs, and renewable energy sources from the outset. Across all asset types, the use of on-site surveys, non-destructive testing, and structural assessments enables the creation of adaptation measures that balance the preservation of heritage, operational effectiveness, and long-term resilience to climate impacts.

3.2.3. Climate Risk Assessment

The climate risk assessment for the “Ex-Caserma Papa” complex takes in consideration the IPCC AR6 framework, where risk is determined as the product of Hazard, Exposure, and Vulnerability. The analysis evaluates climate-related threats such as flooding, using regional climate models and PAI maps to assess *Hazards*.

The *Exposure* is established by factors like the site’s topography, elevation, and orientation, which affect how susceptible the area is to these hazards.

Vulnerability is studied based on construction methods, material longevity, system resilience, and the functional importance of each structure. Both inherent and contextual vulnerabilities are considered. Each building or functional area is then categorized within a four-level climate risk matrix – Low, Medium, High, or Very High – to inform targeted resilience strategies.

Figure 7: Correlation between co-design process and risk matrix.

This matrix facilitates prioritization of adaptation measures and enables the development of a resilience roadmap, tailored to the specific characteristics and uses of the individual structures.

3.2.4. Climate and adaptive vulnerability analysis

Vulnerability is appreciated as a complex, multidimensional concept that involves structural, operational, technological, and regulatory elements.

Physical vulnerability refers to the sensitivity of materials and structures to issues such as thermal stress, moisture infiltration, or deterioration.

Functional vulnerability investigates how accessible a building is, its ability to keep operations, and its reliance on external utilities. Adaptation measures for buildings with regulatory or heritage protections are often restricted.

Climate Vulnerability Index (CVI) conducts together both qualitative and quantitative measures—such as material vulnerability, system redundancy, maintenance data records, and building’s capacity to adapt—to offer an overarching assessment of how susceptible a building is to climate-related risks.

Each factor is assigned a weight based on its relevance, and the resulting CVI is used to rank each building or asset from “Low” to “Very High” vulnerability, supporting prioritization in the overall resilience planning process.

3.2.5. Integrated climate resilience strategies

Following climate risk and vulnerability analysis, a group of targeted adaptation and mitigation strategies proposed to increase climate resilience for the buildings. These action plans are differentiated in compliance with the type of asset involved, acknowledging the different degrees of flexibility, vulnerability, and regulatory constraints across the site.

For existing listed buildings, given the strict conservation requirements imposed by heritage regulations, proposed interventions must be non-invasive, reversible, and materially compatible. General resilience measures that can be included:

- Use of breathable and hygroscopic materials to manage humidity and minimize condensation risks;(It can be applied in: Piazzale, erba e blocchetti.)
- Implementation of passive ventilation systems, such as stack-effect chimneys, to improve air circulation without altering the architectural envelope;
- Installation of reversible sun-shading devices (e.g., brise-soleil, blinds integrated into existing openings);

Regarding underground structures, due to their inherent exposure to hydrogeological risks, a robust set of protection and resilience technologies is recommended:

- Design of redundant drainage and water lifting systems, including sump pumps with backup power supply;
- Installation of watertight closures and flood barriers at entrances and ventilation shafts;
- Application of high-performance waterproofing membranes on retaining walls and floor slabs, with integrated water sensors and alarms.

For newly constructed buildings, that present the opportunity to embed advanced design principles and sustainable technologies from the outset. Recommended strategies include:

- Adoption of bio-architecture principles, including compact forms, orientation optimization, and natural shading;
- Implementation of green roofs and ventilated facades to mitigate heat island effects and improve thermal regulation;
- Use of materials with high thermal inertia, enhancing energy efficiency and indoor comfort during temperature fluctuations;
- Infrastructure for the collection, storage, and reuse of rainwater for irrigation, flushing, or cooling purposes.

In addition to asset-specific interventions, the complex as a whole can be integrated into a broader urban climate resilience framework, supporting systemic adaptation at the neighborhood and municipal scale. This includes:

- Deployment of smart climate monitoring networks, equipped with environmental sensors (temperature, humidity, precipitation, air quality) to support predictive maintenance and emergency response;
- Development of multi-scenario emergency and evacuation plans, accounting for different hazard intensities, population densities, and building uses;
- Alignment with local urban planning tools, including zoning regulations, risk mitigation plans (e.g., PAI), and the Municipal Climate Change Adaptation Plan, ensuring consistency between site-specific interventions and city-wide resilience policies.

Figure 8: Strategies for climate resilience

3.2.6. Monitoring, control, and continuous improvement

Ultimately, the proposed action plan introduces Key Resilience Indicators (KRIs) alongside an ongoing monitoring system to ensure that the climate resilience strategy remains effective and adaptable over time.

That allows to assess the success of implemented actions, refreshing the site’s risk profile in response to new information and regulations, and supporting flexible operations for future changes.

This approach views resilience as an ongoing, adaptive process closely linked to sustainable planning. By bringing together climate science, urban planning, heritage preservation, and engineering innovation, the framework supports the transformation of the “Ex-Caserma Papa” complex into a sustainable, climate-resilient urban centre that maintains both its operational role and cultural significance.

3.2.7. Deterministic Tool

The *INN8-Risk & Resilience Assessment Tool*, developed by RINA-C, provides a comprehensive resilience assessment framework for buildings and urban landscapes. It integrates risk and resilience evaluation into asset management, allowing stakeholders to

quantify vulnerabilities, exposure levels, and potential losses due to various hazards. The tool incorporates probabilistic and deterministic risk models to assess current resilience (AS-IS) and future climate scenarios (TO-BE), offering actionable insights for mitigation and adaptation strategies.

The tool supports decision-making processes by:

- Conducting multi-scale risk and resilience assessments (building, infrastructure, urban district).
- Providing dynamic resilience indicators to evaluate robustness, recovery time, and economic impact.
- Supporting scenario modeling and risk visualization for extreme weather events, structural failures, and climate change impacts.

In the context of risk and resilience analysis for sustainable and adaptive building design, KPIs (see next section) represent essential tools for evaluating and monitoring the resilience, operational continuity, and smart capabilities of buildings. These indicators allow for a data-driven understanding of how well an asset can respond to disruptive events (e.g., climate shocks, energy interruptions) and how it performs in terms of energy efficiency, user interaction, and service quality. The KPIs in the next section (4.1.1 - 4.1.12) are part of a structured assessment methodology aimed at improving the long-term sustainability, functionality, and adaptability of the built environment.

4. RISKS IDENTIFICATION & DESCRIPTION

4.1.1. Urban Heat Island Intensity (KPI 65)

Urban Heat Island Intensity (IUHI) refers to the temperature difference between an urban area and a designated rural reference area. This metric can be applied to various temperature measurements, including canopy air temperature, surface temperature, subsurface (ground) temperature, and atmospheric boundary layer temperature.

In the scientific literature, canopy air temperature is most commonly used when defining IUHI. Therefore, unless otherwise specified, references to Urban Heat Island Intensity in this report pertain to canopy air temperature. The IUHI is typically expressed as:

$$IUHI = T_{\text{urban}} - T_{\text{rural}}$$

Where:

- T_{urban} is the temperature measured within the urban environment.
- T_{rural} is the temperature recorded in a nearby rural or natural area used as a reference.

In situations where direct rural air temperature data are unavailable, the rural reference temperature is generally taken from a nearby airport meteorological station, where such data are commonly collected.

Implications of High Urban Heat Island Intensity

An increased Urban Heat Island Intensity corresponds to a heightened risk of adverse effects, such as:

- Indoor and outdoor thermal discomfort and overheating in buildings.
- Increased heat vulnerability of populations, particularly during heatwaves.
- Elevated energy consumption for cooling systems.

Recent studies have also linked higher IUHI levels to broader societal impacts, including reduced workplace productivity and impaired learning capacity among students [15].

Application in the WILSON Project

Within the scope of the WILSON project, IUHI serves as a key metric for evaluating climate resilience under simulation scenarios, including both the referenced situation ("AS IS") and future projections ("TO BE"). The IUHI is used to quantify the difference in urban temperature scenarios relative to the baseline rural temperature.

The indicator is selected for inclusion in the Deliverable 4.5 *WILSON KPIs life-cycle oriented indicators panel*. It is linked with the *INN6-Environmental performance Toolset*, and it is incorporated in the HIBOU methodology. Moreover, it would be tested in the Italian Demosite: Ex-Caserma Papa UC6.

4.1.2. Outdoor thermal comfort

Outdoor thermal comfort is a key metric for assessing the thermophysiological conditions of open environments, and it holds considerable importance due to its significant impact on social well-being.

Thermal comfort reflects both an individual's perception of local climatic conditions and the combined effects of physiological and psychological factors.

Several indicators have been developed to evaluate thermal comfort in outdoor settings. Among them, the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) [16] is widely recognized—particularly in moderate climate zones—as one of the most comprehensive indices for assessing heat stress in outdoor environments.

The UTCI represents the equivalent air temperature in a standardized reference environment that would produce the same level of physiological strain as that experienced by an individual in the actual environment. Its calculation takes into account multiple climatic parameters, including dry-bulb temperature, mean radiant temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed.

UTCI (°C) range	Stress Category
above +46	extreme heat stress
+38 to +46	very strong heat stress
+32 to +38	strong heat stress
+26 to +32	moderate heat stress
+9 to +26	no thermal stress
+9 to 0	slight cold stress
0 to -13	moderate cold stress
-13 to -27	strong cold stress
-27 to -40	very strong cold stress
below -40	extreme cold stress

Figure 9: Overview of the UTCI thermal stress categories.

The UTCI categorizes thermal stress into ten distinct classes, ranging from below -40°C (extreme cold stress) to above $+46^{\circ}\text{C}$ (extreme heat stress), allowing for a nuanced understanding of thermal conditions across diverse climatic scenarios.

Implications of extreme stress conditions

Heat stress conditions have significant implications for both public health and urban liveability. Prolonged exposure to elevated temperatures can lead to serious health risks, particularly for vulnerable populations such as the elderly, young children, and individuals with pre-existing medical conditions [17].

Application in the WILSON Project

Within the scope of the WILSON project, the UTCI is used as a secondary indicator to assess heat stress conditions under various simulation scenarios, including both the current baseline (“AS IS”) and future projected conditions (“TO BE”).

The UTCI is calculated at pedestrian level in outdoor spaces and allows for quantifying variations in thermal stress relative to baseline conditions.

Although this indicator was not prioritized in Deliverable 4.5 (WILSON KPIs – life-cycle oriented indicators panel), it can serve as a complementary metric to evaluate urban overheating. The UTCI is linked to *INN6-Environmental Performance Toolset* and is integrated into the HIBOU methodology.

Additionally, it is planned to be tested at the Italian pilot: Ex-Caserma Papa UC6.

4.1.3. Restoration Time (100% Capacity) (KPI 66)

This KPI measures the total duration, in days, required to restore a building or infrastructure system to full operational capacity (100%) after an extreme event (e.g., flood, earthquake, heatwave). It covers structural repairs, re-establishment of essential services (electricity, HVAC, water, ICT), and restoring full usability for occupants.

Risk implication

A long restoration time reflects higher vulnerability, disruption of operations, and greater socio-economic impact. Conversely, shorter restoration times indicate higher resilience, improved continuity of services, and better capacity to withstand and recover from extreme events.

Application in the WILSON project

This KPI will be used to assess the recovery capacity of the Italian pilot under UC5 (Risk, resilience and biodiversity nexus). It will be monitored before and after the implementation of adaptive measures to evaluate their effectiveness in reducing downtime and improving resilience planning.

4.1.4. Building Robustness Index (KPI 67)

The Building Robustness Index quantifies the projected loss of functional capacity (expressed as a percentage) of a building when subjected to hazard scenarios. It reflects

both structural and non-structural robustness, considering envelop performance, redundancy of critical systems, and the building's capacity to withstand or limit damage.

Risk implication

A higher percentage of functional capacity loss indicates lower robustness, greater vulnerability, and higher disruption risks. A lower percentage implies stronger resilience, as the building can endure shocks with minimal functional degradation.

Application in the WILSON project

Within UC5 of the Italian pilot, the Building Robustness Index will serve as a comparative metric to evaluate the intrinsic robustness of buildings under different stress-testing or performance-based simulation scenarios. It will help assess the effectiveness of resilience measures in limiting functional degradation during extreme events.

4.1.5. IRES: Resilience Index (KPI 68)

The Resilience Index is a multi-dimensional composite indicator that integrates exposure, sensitivity, adaptive capacity, and redundancy into a single score representing a building's overall resilience. It captures both structural aspects (e.g., materials, design) and operational dimensions (e.g., emergency preparedness, resource management).

Risk implication

A lower resilience score indicates greater vulnerability to hazards, reduced adaptive capacity, and higher risk of disruption. A higher score reflects stronger systemic resilience, better preparedness, and enhanced ability to cope with long-term climate uncertainties.

Application in the WILSON project

In UC5 of the Italian pilot, the Resilience Index will be used to compare systemic resilience across different assets, districts, or design phases. It will support the prioritization of retrofitting strategies and adaptation measures, guiding long-term planning under climate change scenarios.

4.1.6. Direct Losses Quantification (DLQ) (KPI 69)

DLQ represents the monetary value of direct physical damages caused by a hazardous event. It includes losses to structural elements (e.g., slabs, columns), finishes, fixed equipment, and integrated systems such as elevators, electrical panels, or mechanical systems.

Risk implication

High DLQ values indicate greater economic vulnerability and higher financial exposure of the asset to hazards. Lower DLQ values, particularly after mitigation, reflect improved protection, reduced damage, and stronger cost-effectiveness of resilience measures.

Application in the WILSON project

In UC5 of the Italian pilot, DLQ will be applied in cost-benefit analyses and insurance modeling to assess the financial effectiveness of adaptive and mitigation strategies. It will provide a baseline for evaluating economic risks and supporting investment prioritization.

4.1.7. Indirect Losses Quantification (ILQ) (KPI 70)

ILQ estimates the economic impact linked to loss of function, service interruption, reduced productivity, or displacement resulting from building inoperability after a disaster. Unlike direct losses, ILQ does not stem from physical damages but from consequences such as closure of public services, halted operations, or tenant displacement.

Risk implication

High ILQ values indicate significant socioeconomic consequences, especially in critical infrastructure where service continuity is essential (e.g., hospitals, schools, government facilities). Lower ILQ values suggest stronger preparedness and continuity measures, reducing the broader community and economic disruption.

Application in the WILSON project

In UC5 of the Italian pilot, ILQ will be used to evaluate the full socioeconomic impact of hazard events. It will support cost-benefit analyses of continuity strategies and guide the justification of investments in resilience and emergency preparedness.

4.1.8. Level of Service (LoS) (KPI 71)

LoS measures the ability of a building to maintain or rapidly restore its designed service functions under disruption. It accounts for utility availability, accessibility, environmental comfort, safety, and the performance of critical systems across different stress scenarios. The metric includes both passive elements (e.g., envelope performance) and active systems (Mechanical, Electrical, and Plumbing – MEP), enabling a comprehensive resilience assessment.

Risk implication

A low LoS score indicates high vulnerability to service interruptions, reduced user comfort, and operational inefficiency. A high LoS reflects strong functional resilience, better energy efficiency, and improved operational flexibility, reducing risks of service discontinuity in essential buildings.

Application in the WILSON project

In UC5 of the Italian pilot, LoS will be applied to assess functional resilience of buildings, particularly those with critical services. By integrating MEP systems into the analysis, the KPI will help identify risks, dependencies, and opportunities for resilience and efficiency improvements, supporting the prioritization of continuity measures and alignment with district or sectoral resilience goals.

The resilience assessment will not be limited to evaluating the building envelope alone, but will also incorporate the Mechanical, Electrical, and Plumbing (MEP) systems to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of the building's capacity to respond to climate change. The integration of MEP systems into the analysis enables a more holistic understanding of both the active and passive components influencing resilience, energy efficiency, and operational flexibility.

The following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are therefore proposed to assess the Energy and Plant Engineering Vulnerability of the building, with a focus on identifying risks, dependencies, and opportunities for improvement.

4.1.9. Energy Savings and operation (KPI 72)

This KPI evaluates the energy efficiency of the building as a primary metric of sustainability and resilience. Low energy consumption directly contributes to reduced environmental impact and indirectly enhances climate adaptability.

Implications

A well-insulated, energy-efficient building requires less energy to operate and is intrinsically more resilient to climate-related stressors, such as heatwaves or cold spells.

Application in the WILSON project

Performance will be assessed by comparing the Italian demo site's energy metrics with national and international best practices, considering both the current state and the projected improvements after potential retrofitting or optimization.

4.1.10. Respond to user needs (KPI 73)

This KPI measures the ability of the building systems to adapt to dynamic internal and external user needs. Factors such as changes in occupancy, operational use, or user comfort requirements—exacerbated by climate-related variables—must be addressed by flexible and responsive systems.

Implications

A resilient building should be equipped with control strategies and technologies that can absorb variability in demand without significant loss of user comfort.

Application in the WILSON project

This indicator supports the analysis of how well the building can accommodate fluctuating needs without excessive energy use or operational degradation. The construction plan of the Italian Demo will be probably not compliant with Wilson deadlines. Therefore, it will not be possible to evaluate this KPI.

4.1.11. Energy Flexibility Score (KPI 74)

The Energy Flexibility Score quantifies the building's ability to shift or adjust its energy consumption in response to external signals such as grid availability, renewable energy availability, or dynamic energy pricing. This metric reflects how resilient the building is to energy volatility or supply disruptions.

Key components influencing this score include the presence of energy storage systems, the capacity to perform demand-side management, and the degree of grid independence.

Implications

High energy flexibility reduces the risk of service interruptions and enhances the building's contribution to grid stability and decarbonization goals.

Application in the WILSON project

This indicator will be calculated based on the design developed for the Italian Demo, referring to the presence of PV system and/or storages on site to enhance the flexibility of the site.

4.1.12. SRI Score (KPI 75)

The Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) is an EU-standardized metric used to assess a building's capacity to intelligently monitor, control, and automate its energy systems to improve operational efficiency and user comfort.

Implications

The SRI score reflects how well a building can anticipate and respond to external conditions, such as changing weather patterns, energy price signals, and user behaviors.

Application in the WILSON project

RINA has extended the official European Commission methodology by developing a comparative tool that aligns the SRI with BACS classification [18] levels, enabling a direct evaluation of energy saving potential associated with automation system upgrades. This will be applied to the Italian demo site in order to provide evidence of main automation bottlenecks and, therefore, prioritize the interventions to improve building smartness.

PART II: LCA/LCC: ENVIRONMENTAL & SOCIAL ASSESSMENT ON BMS

5. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

To achieve the objective of Tasks 11.4 and 12.4, which consist in developing practical guidelines to integrate Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) into the Building Management System (BMS) to:

- support decision-making for the optimal renovation and planning of buildings by comparing design alternatives;
- identify trade-offs and prioritise sustainability;
- visualise results in an intuitive manner, and
- enable stakeholders to understand the environmental implications of design decisions,

a linear, consecutive, multi-step methodological approach has been adopted.

To better understand how the results of the assessments can facilitate and support the decision-making process, an in-depth literature review of the meaning and potential of LCA, LCC and BMS in building management has been conducted.

Once these three main objectives had been studied and analysed, and their link to the building management sector had been identified, work began on developing the practical guidelines.

This process has been divided into two consecutive and interdependent time frames, in which the results of the first constitute the starting point for the second. In details:

- **From M10 to M18**, i.e. the time allocated for the development of **Task 11.4** and Deliverable 11.3, the data requirements and sources necessary for conducting the LCA and LCC analyses have been introduced, together with a conceptual version of the data flow architecture specific to the integration of LCA and LCC services within the WILSON environment. The main outcome of this initial work, as reported in this document, is the identification of the key technical issues that must be addressed in the next phase to ensure the proper integration and operation of the LCA and LCC services into BMS and WILSON environment;
- **From M18 to M30**, i.e. the time allocated for the development of **Task 12.4** and Deliverable 12.3, all the technical issues must be addressed and resolved. This will enable the development of practical guidelines that can provide concrete support for the implementation of LCA and LCC within the BMS, while also being aligned with the data flow infrastructure and objectives of the WILSON project. These guidelines will be divided into three main sections, organised according to a simple and intuitive logic:
 1. Data Requirements and Sources: This section identifies all the data necessary for conducting an LCA and LCC assessment has been identified, along with the relevant sources. These include material data, operational data, maintenance data, cost data, and technical information derived from BIM models, digital twins and PDHs;
 2. Integration of LCA and LCC into BMS: Architecture and Logics: The most technical section of the report. It indicates the BMS requirements for conducting LCA and LCC assessments, as well as the LCA/LCC assessment data flows and

computational logics, including the assessment method, system boundaries, functional units, and key performance indicators;

3. Decision Support and Stakeholder Engagement: This section provides practical guidelines for visualising LCA and LCC results, both for the current scenario and alternatives. It includes methods for comparing results and using them to support the decision-making, in selecting the most sustainable solution from a techno-environmental and social perspective.

The three sections together will provide comprehensive guidelines for implementing LCA and LCC approaches within the BMS, to support the decision-making process towards the most sustainable design choices and alternatives.

This proposed methodological approach will ensure that the guidelines developed in Task 12.4 will be fully aligned with, and implementable within, the WILSON project and environment.

For a clearer overview, this approach has been outlined in the form of a simple workflow scheme in Figure 10 below.

Figure 10: Multi-Step Methodological Approach Proposed for Task 11.4 and Task 12.4.

6. LITERATURE REVIEW AND STATE OF THE ART OF LCA AND LCC IN SUSTAINABLE BUILDING MANAGEMENT

6.1. Introduction to LCA and LCC in Built Environment

As mentioned in the previous description of the methodological approach, the first step in developing practical guidelines for implementing LCA and LCC in BMS is to understand:

- What LCA and LCC are;
- What the main standards are and what their scope of application is;
- What LCA and LCC can be used for.

To answer these questions and provide a clear and structured introduction to LCA and LCC in the built environment, the following table has been developed. This approach allows for parallel analysis while minimizing repetition.

Table 1: Introduction to LCA

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	
What is LCA?	The European Environment Agency (EEA) defines LCA as “a process of evaluating the effects that a product has on the environment over the entire period of its life, thereby increasing resource-use efficiency and decreasing liabilities. It can be used to study the environmental impact of either a product or the function the product is designed to perform” [19].
What are the main standards and what is their scope of application?	Main Standards and Frameworks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO 14040:2006 – Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Principles and framework (General Level); • ISO 14044:2006 – Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Requirements and guidelines (General Level); • ISO 14025:2006 – Environmental labels and declarations – Type III environmental declarations – Principles and procedures (Product Declaration); • ISO 21930:2017 – Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works – Core rules for environmental product declarations of construction products and services (Construction Product); • EN 15804:2012 + A2:2019/AC:2021 – Sustainability of construction works – Environmental product declarations – Core rules for the product category of construction products (EU – Construction Product); • EN 15978:2011 – Sustainability of construction works – Assessment of environmental performance of buildings – Calculation method (EU – Building Level); • ILCD Handbook (JRC, EU) – International Reference Life Cycle Data System Handbook, EU Guidelines for LCA (EU – General Level)

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C-PCR-029 – COMPLEMENTARY PRODUCT CATEGORY RULES (C-PCR) TO PCR 2019:14 (EPD) – LCA guidelines for building assessments. • COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION (EU) 2021/2279 – Commission Recommendation on the use of the Environmental Footprint methods to measure and communicate the life cycle environmental performance of products and organisations (General Level); • Level(s) – European framework for sustainable buildings (Building Level).
What can LCA be used for?	<p>According to [20], LCA can be used in the built environment to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate the environmental impact of buildings during the early design stages, helping designers to make environmentally informed decisions (e.g. material selection) and identify design alternatives with a lower environmental impact. However, this approach can be affected by the large number of uncertainties relating to the initial stages of the construction process, as well as the lack of detailed information. • Assess the environmental impact of renovation and retrofit solutions to identify the most suitable option. In this case, the main barrier can be the potential high cost of data collection, if specific BIM models or data repositories are unavailable.

Table 2: Introduction to LCC

Life Cycle Costing (LCC)	
What is LCC?	<p>The Article 68 of Directive 2014/24/EU and the Article 83 of Directive 2014/25/EU define the Life Cycle Costing (LCC) as the evaluation of “<i>all the costs that will be incurred during the lifetime of the product, work or service</i>”². This includes the purchase price, operating costs, maintenance costs, end-of-life costs, residual values, and environmental externalities (e.g. those connected to GHG emissions)².</p>
What are the main standards and what is their scope of application?	<p>Main Standards and Frameworks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 15643:2021 – Sustainability of construction works – Framework for assessment of buildings and civil engineering works • ISO 15686-5:2017 – Buildings and constructed assets – Service life planning, Part 5: Life-cycle costing (Building Level); • EN 16627:2015 – Sustainability of construction works – Assessment of economic performance of buildings – Calculation methods (EU – Building Level);

² [Life-cycle costing – EU Definition](#), Date accessed: 09 September 2025

Life Cycle Costing (LCC)	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEC 60300-3-3 – Dependability management – Application guide – Life cycle costing (General Level).
What can LCC be used for?	<p>In the built environment, LCC can be used to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support informed decision-making by evaluating all costs associated with a project over its lifecycle, including initial, operating, long-term maintenance, replacement and disposal costs³; • reduce total building costs over the building’s useful life by selecting technologies with lower maintenance costs, energy-efficient solutions, and durable materials³; • minimise the environmental impact of buildings by reducing energy consumption by selecting efficient assets and minimising waste³; • increase building value and longevity by investing in high-quality, durable materials³. <p>LCC can be applied to both the design and renovation/retrofitting phases. However, as previously mentioned with regard to LCA assessments in buildings, the quality of an LCC can potentially be affected by uncertainties relating to the initial stages of the construction process and the lack of detailed information.</p>

6.2. Literature review of BIM & BMS in sustainable building management

In the context of a construction sector seeking for different alternatives to lower environmental impacts related to energy consumption and resource depletion, two digital technologies have emerged as critical enablers for sustainable transformation: Building Information Modelling (BIM) and Building Management Systems (BMS). This chapter will analyse the current state of research and practice on the integration of BIM and BMS, with a specific focus on design and retrofitting projects and their impact on energy efficiency and material optimization.

BIM provides a digital representation of a building's physical and functional characteristics. In sustainable building management, BIM is instrumental for condition assessment, simulation of design alternatives, and material inventory. Different studies highlight that BIM-based workflows enable precise planning and visualization of sustainability interventions, significantly improving resource efficiency and reducing construction waste. BIM also facilitates energy modelling through tools like Revit, IES-VE, or DesignBuilder, supporting comparative analyses of design options based on energy performance and environmental impact [21]. In addition to this, BIM supports user's decision-making by generating accurate Bills of Materials allowing to forecast material needs and compare different scenarios to reduce embodied emissions and promoting circular economy principles.

³ [Cerclos - Benefits of Lifecycle Costing](#), Date accessed: 09 September 2025

BMS are integrated control systems that monitor and manage building operations in real-time, including HVAC, lighting, ventilation, and energy systems. BMS plays a central role in reducing operational energy use, improving occupant comfort, and enabling predictive maintenance. In retrofitted buildings, installing or upgrading a BMS is often a high-priority intervention to enhance operational efficiency. Moreover, BMS can promote environmental KPI's monitoring as indoor air quality (IAQ) and daylight usage, both directly related to energy efficiency and user's health and wellness. Combining BMS applications with renewable energy systems can further enhance sustainability into green building management.

The integration of BIM and BMS represents a promising frontier for sustainable building management. BIM provides the static, structured representation of building elements and systems, while BMS delivers dynamic, real-time operational data.

One of the most significant synergies lies in energy performance optimization. BIM models enriched with sensor data from BMS allow facility managers to visualize energy flows, occupancy patterns, and equipment performance within the digital environment. This enables more accurate calibration of control strategies, enhancing an optimization of the energy used [22].

In terms of material consumption, BIM–BMS integration can facilitate the tracking of material degradation and lifecycle status. Maintenance records and sensor data (e.g., vibration, temperature, humidity) collected through BMS can be linked to specific building components in the BIM model. This linkage supports proactive replacement planning, minimizes unscheduled downtime, and extends the lifespan of building assets, all contributing to material conservation.

6.3. State of the art of LCA and LCC in sustainable building management

As illustrated in Table 1 and Table 2, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) are tools for evaluating the sustainability and economic viability of buildings throughout their entire lifespan, from the early design stages to renovation scenario evaluation.

Indeed, one of the main objectives of LCA and LCC in the context of sustainable building management is to provide scientific support for data-driven decision-making, enabling stakeholders to compare design alternatives based on their environmental and financial performance.

According to recent research, the integration of LCA and LCC into the design process significantly improve the capacity to select optimal design and retrofit strategies, avoiding impact burden shifting or costly long-term consequences [23]. The convergence of LCA and LCC within BIM frameworks marks a significant advancement in sustainable building management. BIM serves as a common data environment that hosts geometry, materials, quantities, and specifications, which are essential inputs for both LCA and LCC calculations.

This integration supports a more holistic and systemic evaluation accounting for both environmental and financial impacts across the building's lifecycle.

Regarding Building Management Systems (BMS), the assimilation of LCA-LCC into real-time monitoring tools represents a novel frontier into sustainable building operations. This integration enables the dynamic updating of life cycle performance indicators based on real-time data, such as energy usage, lightning and HVAC programming. Similarly, maintenance records and equipment runtime data can inform LCC models by updating service life assumptions and operational cost estimates.

Emerging practices involve integrating LCA directly into BIM-BMS workflows through plug-ins and APIs. For instance, OneClick LCA provides a Revit plug-in that enables automated extraction of material quantities from the BIM model and real-time LCA analysis. Tally, another widely used tool, operates within Revit to assess embodied carbon of construction elements. The automation of LCA within BIM not only accelerates the process but also allows for scenario testing during design development. Designers and energy consultants can simulate the effects of alternative insulation materials, structural systems, or finishings on the building's environmental profile.

Despite this promising scenario, several challenges hinder the full implementation of LCA and LCC in digital twin applications. Available high-quality data is not always accessible and consistent across the regions, and the reliance on complex tools and costly databases can difficult the integration. Moreover, the interoperability of LCA-LCC tools with digital twin technologies remains a barrier to tackle in the following years, with differences in data formats and software languages complicate seamless data exchange. Most LCA-LCC tools are not natively designed to interface with real-time systems or 3D digital environments, requiring customized APIs, middleware, or manual data handling.

Maintaining synchronicity between static design-stage models and dynamically changing operational data poses a methodological challenge, particularly in ensuring that the life cycle indicators remain up to date and actionable. Overcoming these barriers will require harmonized standards, open-access data platforms, and stronger collaboration between software developers, sustainability experts, and building operators.

7. GUIDELINES DEVELOPMENT FOUNDATIONS – CONCEPTUAL INTRODUCTION

This document represents a preliminary work serving as the starting point for the development of guidelines on integrating LCA and LCC into Building Management Systems.

At this stage, the focus is on providing a high-level overview of the data requirements to be supplied by the different actors in the network, and the structure and logics of the data flow involved in integration process.

More detailed technical specifications, case-based applications, and refined workflows will be developed and presented in the second version of this report, ensuring a progressive enhancement of guidance aligned with project advancements, as previously illustrated in Figure 10.

7.1. Data Requirements and Sources

For the correct integration of LCA and LCC approaches into BMS utilization it is crucial to enhance the interoperability of different data types and sources, understanding how this information can be translated into correct inputs for LCA and LCC calculation. BMS applications normally focus on real-time energy performance and operational control. On the contrary, integrating LCA approach into BMS applications requires a broader perspective where environmental and economic impacts are measured across the life cycle of the building.

The multiple data requirements cover different domains as construction and design, operational monitoring and financial planning, each one demanding specific logics and treatment. For these purposes, the main data categories are Material Data, mostly characteristics and quantities coming from the BIM models; Operational Data, collected through sensors and other devices connected to the BMS application; Cost Data, derived from design-stage documentation (e.g. Bill of Quantities), energy supplier information and historical databases. These datasets must be properly managed to ensure smooth transfer from APIs to PDHs, enhancing interoperability with proxies coming from public LCA and LCC datasets. These datasets will enable the calculation of the environmental and techno-economic indicators that were proposed in Task 4.5 and that are necessary for informed decision-making.

7.1.1. Material Data

This type of data provides the information for assessing the embodied environmental impacts of building construction and retrofitting projects. Raw materials extraction and production account for a significant share of life cycle environmental impacts, being essential to provide accurate material information. This data includes information as geometry, volume, density of the components involved in the studied scenario, key for calculating embodied emissions belonging to the stages A1-A3 of a building life cycle information [24]. Moreover, end-of-life information on recycling and reuse strategies, as well as dismantling operations, is important to cover all relevant stages.

Material data is generated within BIM models and potentially archived in the data space, where it can be accessed by BMS users through the PDH, supporting the visualization of “AS-IS” and “TO-BE” scenarios.

7.1.2. Operational data

This type of data provides information for calculating environmental impacts related to energy and resource consumption during the use phase (B1-B7) of a building life cycle information [24]. Sensor and IoT devices provide a network capable of measuring real-time data enabling the dynamic measurement of environmental and economic performance. This type of data includes:

- Energy consumption: Direct measurements of electricity and gas utilization, if possible, broken down by destination (illumination, HVAC systems, plug loads, etc)
- Water consumption: Direct measurements of water utilization within the building.
- Equipment runtime and maintenance: Information about device consumption, updating services life assumptions and replacement schedules.

Within the BMS application, operational data from sensors and monitoring devices is published in real time, providing the basis for evaluating environmental impacts and updating economic performance indicators.

7.1.3. Cost data

Cost data supports LCC assessment by adding economic parameters to the data categories mentioned above, ensuring that sustainable designs are financially viable. Initial investments, operation & maintenance activities, and end-of-life estimations are managed within the context of BIM and BMS applications in order to connect environmental and economic performance.

Cost data can be divided in:

- CAPEX: Material and labor costs, equipment procurement and commissioning.
- OPEX: Energy bills, water expenses and maintenance costs
- End-of-life: Deconstruction, waste management, and recycling costs.

Cost data is provided by suppliers through Material Passport data and stored within the BIM models, following the same direction of Material data.

7.1.4. Proxies

This type of data directly links the primary data just described with the environmental and economic indicators required for the LCA and LCC assessment, applying emissions factors and expense data from standardised databases and public sources to ensure consistency and filling missing data.

This category includes supplier’s products specific declarations as EPDs, and national EPD Systems, assigning environmental factors to materials coming from the BIM model. For this

purpose, embodied carbon databases could be useful for the calculation of GHG emissions related to the construction and development phase of the building. On the other hand, public databases (e.g. DEFRA,) and national grid information can provide emission factors for use-phase consumption data, enhancing the possibilities of dynamic performance within the BMS application.

7.2. Integration of LCA and LCC into BMS: Architecture and Logics

7.2.1. Introduction

The integration of LCA and LCC analyses into Building Management Systems (BMS) requires the development of a solid and structured IT Architecture, capable of managing significant flows of information, complex calculation logics and clear systems for visualizing and interpreting results.

Based on the information presented in Section 7.1, which introduced the necessary data for the LCA and LCC analyses, the related sources and the archiving methods, Section 7.2 describes the IT Architecture and computational logic behind transforming this information into comprehensive environmental and economic assessments.

The scope of this Chapter is to introduce the conceptual structure behind integrating LCA and LCC into BMS from an IT and logics perspective. This chapter will lay the groundwork for the practical guidelines that will be fully developed in Task 12.4.

7.2.2. Data Flow Architecture and LCA & LCC Logics. Concept

The data flow architecture developed within the WILSON Project consists of a series of functional components, each of which is designed with specific tasks and responsibilities.

Figure 11 provides an overview of the current IT Architecture.

Figure 11: Data Flow Architecture (Source WILSON Deliverable 5.1).

The WILSON Project focuses its attention on secondary data usage, making existing data available for advanced applications and value-added services. Among these, the LCA and LCC Service is particularly important, as it can support:

- optimising renovation and building planning through decision-making based on design alternative comparisons;
- identifying of trade-offs and prioritising sustainability;
- visualising LCA and LCC results in an intuitive manner; and
- enabling stakeholders to understand the environmental implications of design decisions.

To focus the discussion on implementing LCA and LCC analysis within the BMS, a simplified conceptual data flow architecture⁴, tailored for this specific case study, is presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Case Study. LCA & LCC Implementation, simplified conceptual data flow architecture

Five main interconnected components are identified. In order:

- **Data Sources:** it refers to all the input data necessary to conduct LCA and LCC analyses. The data required for conducting the assessments have been identified in the previous section (section 7.1) and can be summarised in material data, operational data, cost data and secondary (proxy) data;
- **Data Space:** it is a distributed infrastructure that connects data providers and consumers via standardised interfaces, protocols, and semantic models (WILSON Deliverable D5.1). Data sharing is based on the principles of data sovereignty, interoperability, and trust. Ideally, the Data Space should represent the environment in which data from external providers (such as public LCA and LCC databases) are made available to internal applications.
- **Personalised Building Data Hubs (PDH):** it is a decentralised integration layer that supports the management of heterogeneous building data (WILSON Deliverable 7.1). It aggregates and harmonises information from various sources, such as BIM, IoT sensors, BMS, ERP and legacy databases, making it accessible in a secure and interoperable way (WILSON Deliverable 7.1). Acting as a local orchestrator, it provides unified interfaces, semantic enrichment and access control, and can function as both a provider and consumer of data, enabling trusted exchanges (WILSON

⁴ Simplified means that only main functional components have been reported, while conceptual means that it is a first draft and architectural changes are possible in task 12.4.

Deliverable 7.1). Ideally, the PDH should represent the environment through which building-specific data, together with data provided by the Data Space, is made available to the LCA and LCC services.

- **LCA & LCC Service:** it is one of the possible value-added services that can be implemented within the WILSON environment. To enable this, the system network must provide all the necessary data to the LCA & LCC Service, ensuring completeness, interoperability, and traceability. Then, the service can perform the assessments and generate the outcomes. To support the decision-making process and allow comparison between actual and alternative design configurations, the outcomes should be presented in numerical and graphical formats, including specific LCA and LCC KPIs. The ultimate goal is to present the outcomes in a way that is easy for all key stakeholders to understand.
- **User Interface for BMS Managers:** it plays a central role in the data flow architecture promoted by the WILSON project, representing the operational core for building monitoring and control (WILSON Deliverable 9.1). Ideally, the BMS should act as the primary interface through which stakeholders can access to LCA and LCC assessments and view the results.

As the data flow architecture for implementing LCA and LCC analysis into BMS and WILSON environment is still under development, with several items yet to be discussed, the explanation proposed should be considered as a conceptual introduction to the objectives of the task.

Consequently, in the next version of the report (D12.3), in addition to provide more details about the data flow architecture, logical steps and procedures for carrying out LCA and LCC will be presented. This will include details on:

- how to log in to the BMS;
- how to set LCA-LCC essential parameters;
- what are the results of the assessment (KPIs and Plots);
- how to interpret and evaluate the study results;
- how the assessments can support the decision support system.

All these aspects will also be illustrated through a practical example, created for the Italian demo site and referring to Use Case 6, entitled “Renovation Planning and Design”, which is particularly suitable for showing the application of these guidelines.

For this reason, to avoid releasing guidelines that may change within the next months, they will be published directly in D12.3 in M30.

Finally, to guide the discussion and development of the second phase of the assessment, the following section presents the main technical points under discussion, together with considerations regarding ideal and realistic cases, and the required next steps.

7.3. Pending technical points and next steps

This section outlines the key technical topics that will be investigated during the next project phase (M18–M30). The aim is to use these issues to guide future discussions towards developing a feasible, optimised data flow architecture and logic that can serve as a concrete example for creating practical guidelines for integrating LCA and LCC studies into the BMS.

The main technical topics are explained in the table below, together with corresponding next steps to be covered in task 12.4, to provide comprehensive guidelines in D12.3.

Table 3: List of technical points to be assessed between M18 and M30 and next steps

Item #	Technical Point	Next Steps (M18–M30)
1	Investigate how the PDH and the data space can share secondary (proxy) data from external databases and sources with the BMS.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initiate discussions with the partners responsible for developing the PDH and Data Space to assess the integration of external sources necessary for LCA and LCC analyses within the environment promoted by the WILSON project. Some of these sources have already been identified in Deliverable 12.2 “Methodology for climate & biodiversity impacts”. It is necessary to verify whether the WILSON architecture allows for effective connection with these sources, so as to simplify data access for stakeholders.
2	Investigate how the data from different sources, such as material data from BIM models and operational data from BMS systems, can be made available to end users. Investigate the feasibility of developing a “Building Life Cycle Inventory Widget/Frontend” that can support the BMS and enable users to efficiently collect and visualise all building-related information relevant for conducting LCA and LCC analyses in a single place. This would address one of the main challenges of LCA/LCC analyses: data collection. It would also represent an important achievement in line with the WILSON objectives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continue the discussion with the partner in charge of developing the WILSON architecture and functional components to address the technical point or identify alternative solutions in line with WILSON objectives.
3	Investigate whether it is possible to assign emission and cost factors to each of the data collected by the Building Life Cycle Inventory Widget, ideally handled automatically (e.g. through direct link with Material Passports) or manually (e.g. using external databases).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The actions relating to technical point 2 depend on the outcome of the previous technical issue.

Item #	Technical Point	Next Steps (M18–M30)
4	Investigate how building input data can be processed by LCA and LCC service. The LCA/LCC software currently available on the market is often complex and requires specific technical skills to use effectively. One possible solution would be to develop a simple, intuitive tool able to support decision-makers. This tool should be able to receive the automatically generated summary file (which has been edited and validated by the stakeholders) and process the data to provide simplified, easily interpretable results.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP11/12 internal discussion to understand the level of complexity of the service to propose an identification of the most technically feasible solution.
5	Investigate whether it is possible to store both the input and output data from the LCA and LCC analysis within the WILSON environment, i.e. via PDH using APIs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue the discussion with the partner in charge of developing the PDH to address this technical point or identify alternative solutions in line with WILSON objectives.
6	Define how to access the BMS and the LCA and LCC interfaces, where the outcomes of the analysis can be visualised and possibly downloaded.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue the discussion with the partners in charge of developing the PDH and the BMS to address this technical point.
7	Define the characteristics of the LCA and LCC interface for displaying evaluation results.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP11/12 Internal discussion to define the BMS front-end appearance, the types of plots to be displayed, and the indicators to be assessed.

8. CONCLUSIONS

This report, entitled *“Risk and Vulnerability & LCA/LCC Integration”*, sets out key guidelines and specifications for the development of climate risk and vulnerability indicators, together with practical recommendations for integrating LCA and LCC into BMS. These guidelines are intended to support building and district rehabilitation, as well as circular renovation strategies, in alignment with the broader objectives of the WILSON project.

The report introduces two main innovations:

- **The HIBOU method** (Hybrid assessment of the Impacts and Benefits of nature-based solutions in Urban systems), which enables the assessment of:
 - Environmental footprint (Climate Change and Biodiversity – ex situ, based on Life Cycle Assessment),
 - Impacts on in situ biodiversity,
 - Urban Heat Island effects,
 based on a shared ontology developed within the WILSON framework to ensure consistency and interoperability across applications.
- **The Risk & Resilience Assessment Tool**, which focuses on evaluating risk and resilience within asset management processes. It enables stakeholders to quantify vulnerabilities, exposure levels, and potential losses across different climate-related hazards.

In addition, the integration of LCA and LCC into BMS applications is presented as a promising opportunity to facilitate the calculation of environmental and financial indicators directly within operational building management environments. This integration enhances sustainable decision-making, supports efficient building management, and promotes stakeholder engagement in renovation and retrofitting scenarios.

Key Achievements:

- Development of a structured methodology addressing the nexus between Material Resource Consumption, Climate Change, Risk, Resilience, and Biodiversity, based on a consistent and harmonized framework.
- Improvement of modelling approaches enabling the calculation KPIs through a common ontology applicable to urban-scale challenges.
- Identification of the main challenges associated with integrating LCA and LCC into BMS applications. The intrinsic methodological complexity of LCA and LCC represents a significant constraint within already complex digital systems. Even simplified assumptions may evolve into critical issues that compromise the reliability of environmental and economic assessments. Furthermore, limited availability of high-quality data and the lack of technical LCA/LCC expertise among system actors may reduce practical usability, or in extreme cases, hinder full integration of the approach.
- Definition of a conceptual framework outlining the LCA and LCC methodological structure, data requirements, and logical architecture necessary for implementation.

Pilot Implementation:

The Italian pilot site, Ex-Caserma Papa in Brescia, serves as a case study to implement the proposed approaches. The analysis focuses on risk, resilience, biodiversity interactions, and renovation planning strategies.

Preliminary work on input data collection has highlighted the complexity of integrating data within ongoing construction and renovation processes. This underlines the need for flexible methodologies and solutions tailored to site-specific conditions.

The improved methodological framework, supported by the common ontology, will be applied to compute the defined KPIs across different scenarios of the Italian pilot. This enables structured decision-making through a multicriteria assessment approach.

Future Developments

Further developments will focus on:

- Strengthening interoperability between digital tools to enable automated data exchange and KPI computation.
- Finalizing methodological developments related to Urban Heat Island assessment.
- Completing scenario-based input data consolidation and simulation processes.
- Implementing and validating UHI-related tools within the Italian pilot, including simulation, KPI calculation, and results interpretation.
- Developing practical operational guidelines in collaboration with project partners to progressively integrate LCA and LCC requirements into digital building management environments. These guidelines will include workflow logic, operational instructions, and recommendations for interpreting results, serving as a structured manual for the technological solution developed.

At this stage, the LCA framework prioritizes Global Warming Potential (GWP) as the main environmental indicator, ensuring methodological alignment and simplifying implementation for partners with limited LCA experience. As digital tools mature, the inclusion of additional environmental impact categories may be considered in future phases.

This report highlights the importance of developing an interoperable IT structure capable of harmonizing diverse datasets delivered to end users through multiple interconnected applications within the WILSON framework. Such interoperability enables different system actors to provide robust and consistent information, which is essential for evaluating alternative “as-is” and “to-be” scenarios aligned with financial, environmental, and sustainability objectives.

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